

A proposal: physician as a critical thinker

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CanMEDS (by The Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Canada) is a framework that identifies and describes the abilities physicians require to effectively meet the health care needs of the people they serve. A competent physician has to integrate seven roles described by CanMEDS framework, and these are medical expert (the integrating role), communicator, collaborator, leader, health advocate, scholar and professional. The CanMEDS framework has also been implemented in Croatian postgraduate specialist studies as a part of general competencies of every specialist doctor.

Here, in this short commentary, I would like to propose another important role that I think every physician should accomplish, and that is of a **critical thinker**. Jon Jureidini (research leader) and Leemon B. McHenry (professor emeritus) argued in their article "**The illusion of evidence based medicine**" that the validity of the evidence based medicine paradigm depends on reliable data from clinical trials, most of which are conducted by the pharmaceutical industry and reported in the names of senior academics. Taking into account that the industry sponsored clinical trials are misrepresented to some degree, the evidence based medicine remains an illusion. Authors continue to explain that universities adopted a

neo-liberal market approach, actively seeking pharmaceutical funding on commercial terms, and therefore, became instruments of industry, whilst academics became agents for the promotion of commercial product through company control of the research agenda, ghostwriting of medical journal articles and continuing medical education (also sponsored by pharmaceutical industry). Regulators are funded by pharmaceutical industry and then use industry funded and performed clinical trials to approve drugs, without even seeing the raw data in most cases. At the end of this remarkable article authors proposed a reform that would include liberation of regulators from drug company funding, taxation imposed on pharmaceutical companies to allow public funding of independent trials and anonymised individual patient level trial data posted, along with study protocols, on suitably accessible websites so that third parties could rigorously evaluate the methodology and trial results.

Taking into account the above-mentioned facts, I think that there is a need to implement the training of physicians as, of industry and politics independent critical thinkers, in order to improve their ability to critically evaluate clinical trial results, and all other scientific and clinical

evidence available in the literature, as well as to be able to identify the problem and suggest a possible solution without fear for retaliation or censorship. In order to shape a physician as a critical thinker the following competencies are required: general medical knowledge and skills as well as medical knowledge and skills specific to the field of expertise (overlaps with medical expert role); basic or advanced skills related to evidence based medicine (correct interpretation of journal articles, clinical trials, scientific and clinical guidelines); basics of biostatistics (in order to be able to interpret the results of a trial); and finally, knowledge of bioethics and basic knowledge of medical law (both national and international).

REFERENCES

1. CanMEDS. Available at <https://www.royalcollege.ca/rcsite/canmeds/canmeds-framework-e> (cited on June 15, 2022)
2. Jureidini J, McHenry LB. The illusion of evidence based medicine. *BMJ* 2022;376:o702. doi:10.1136/bmj.o702